

Effect of chitosan and mordants on the dyeability of cotton fabrics with a natural dye from the barks of *Odina wodier* Roxb.

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Abstract : This work has focused on developing eco-friendly treatments for modifying the fabric surface. In the present study, the cotton fabric was treated with chitosan at different concentrations to find a suitable concentration on the dyeability with a natural dye from the barks of *Odina wodier* Roxb. The influence of dyeing methods with mordants, i.e. pre-mordanting, post-mordanting and simultaneous mordanting was determined. The light and wash fastness of chitosan treated samples were measured and compared with untreated samples. Chitosan-treated cotton fabrics improved both in dyeability and fastness compared with untreated cotton fabric. The cotton fabrics treated with chitosan not only provided better depth of shade but also provided better wash fastness and light fastness than those of the untreated fabrics. The use of different mordants and mordanting methods affected the dye shade and depth of shade differently on the dyed fabrics both with and without chitosan. The range of colour developed on the dyed materials were evaluated in terms of ($L^*a^*b^*$) CIELAB coordinates and the dye absorption on the cotton was studied by using K/S values.

Keywords : Natural dye, *Odina wodier*, chitosan, mordant and cotton fabric.

Introduction

A dye is a coloured substance which can be made to adhere to fabrics such as cotton, silk, wool, etc. Natural dyes are obtained from flowers, barks, seeds, shrubs, berries, leaves, insects and minerals. These dyes have been used for centuries to produce colours for fabrics, yarns, leather, food, etc. Natural dyes can give subtle and soft colours through the brightest colour to the yarns and fabrics¹. Natural dyes exhibit better biodegradability and generally have a better compatibility with the environment. Also they possess lower toxicity and allergic reactions than synthetic dyes².

Chitosan (Fig. 1) is a polymer obtained from deacetylation of chitin, is a cationic polysaccharide with

Fig. 1. Structure of chitosan.

linear chain consisting of β -(1,4)-linked 2-acetamino-2-deoxy- β -D-glucopyranose and 2-amino-2-deoxy- β -D-glucopyranose. Chitosan is used in dietary supplements, water treatment, food preservation, agriculture, cosmetics, paper, medicinal application and fabric modification³. There has been a large increase in chitosan research during the past decade. This is due to its biocompatibility, biodegradability, non-toxicity, and other unique properties such as film forming ability, chelation and adsorption properties and antimicrobial activity. It is a deacetylated chitin produced from prawn shells, shrimp shells, crab shells, fly larva shells and squid pens⁴.

Odina wodier is a large tall tree (Fig. 1) found in deciduous forest in India, Myanmar, Srilanka, China, Malaysia, Cambodia and Philippine Islands. It is popularly known as Kashmala, Odiamaram and in English it is called Rhusodina. The dried and powdered bark is found to use as tooth powder by poor villagers. The bark extract has been reported to be useful in vaginal trouble, curing ulcer, heart diseases etc.⁵.

Materials and methods :

Materials :

Source : The barks of *Odina wodier* was collected from Saliangalam village, Thanjavur District as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2. *Odina wodier* tree.

Fig. 3. Barks of *Odina wodier*.

Substrates : Bleached cotton fabric was used for natural dyeing.

Chemicals used : AR grade metallic salts such as copper sulphate, ferrous sulphate, alum, potassium dichromate, nickel sulphate and stannous chloride were used as chemical mordants.

Experimental

Dye extraction : Barks of tree were cut into small pieces and soaked in distilled water and heated in a beaker kept over a water bath for 2 h to facilitate quick extraction. Then it was filtered and the filtrate was collected in a separate beaker.

Preparation of chitosan solution : Chitosan solutions were prepared at 0.25%, 0.5%, 0.75% and 1.0% con-

centrations. Each amount of chitosan was dissolved in 1% acetic acid and left overnight at room temperature. Then the solution was filtered to remove any insoluble materials and it was used for treatment⁶.

Pre-treatment of chitosan on cotton fabrics : Cotton fabrics were pre-treated by each chitosan solution. Chitosan treated cotton fabrics were dried at 100 °C for 5 min. After that, treated fabrics were dyed with the dye solution⁶.

Dyeing procedure : The chitosan treated and untreated cotton fabrics were dyed with dye extract keeping M : L ratio as 1 : 30. Dyeing was carried out at 80 °C and continued for 1 h.

Mordanting : The chitosan treated and untreated cotton fabrics were treated with different chemical mordants by following three methods⁷.

(i) *Pre-mordanting :* In this method, cotton fabrics were pretreated with the solution of different chemical and then dyed with the dye extract.

(ii) *Post-mordanting :* In this method, dyed cotton fabrics were treated with a solution of different chemical mordants.

(iii) *Simultaneous mordanting :* In this method, the cotton fabrics were dyed with the dye extract as well as different chemical mordants.

Colour fastness : The dyed samples were tested according to IS standards. Colour fastness to washing and light fastness were determined from standard test methods IS-687-79 and IS-2454-85 respectively.

Measurement of colour strength : The spectral reflectances of the dyed samples were measured using a Text flash spectrophotometer (Data colour corp.). The *K/S* values were calculated by Kubelka-Munk equation.

$$K/S = (1 - R)^2/2R$$

where *R* is the decimal fraction of the reflectance of the dyed samples at λ_{\max} . *K* is the absorption coefficient and *S* is scattering coefficient⁸.

Results and discussion

Preparation and optimization of aqueous extract of Odina wodier : The barks of *Odina wodier* were found to discharge colour in hot water very easily. Increasing the quantity of barks 5 g to 20 g per 100 mL water boiled for

1 h is accompanied with the increase in colour strength and depth in colour. It was observed that, colour of the dye extract was dark red colour as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Aqueous extract from barks of *Odina wodier*.

Optimization of chitosan concentration : The results in Table 1 showed the colour strength. The *K/S* values of all chitosan-treated fabrics had higher values than the

the fabric stiffer and a bit yellower than untreated fabrics. In this research, 1% chitosan concentration was used for dyeing of cotton fabric because of desirable stiffness in fabric.

Dyeing behavior of the dye extract : The cotton fabrics (both chitosan treated and untreated fabrics) were dyed with chemical mordants. It was observed that, the dye uptake was found to be good in post mordanting method. Post mordanting method showed a higher depth of shade than that of other two methods is shown in Fig. 5.

Effect of mordants and chitosan on dyed fabrics : The effect of mordants on colour intensity (*K/S*) of chitosan-treated and untreated fabric was examined by Text flash spectrophotometer. The effect of mordants on *K/S* value and colour differences of dyed fabrics treated with 1%

Table 1. *K/S* values of chitosan treated cotton fabric at different concentrations

Chitosan concentrations (%)	Chitosan treated cotton fabric				Chitosan treated cotton fabric with dyeing			
	<i>L</i> *	<i>a</i> *	<i>b</i> *	<i>K/S</i> at 400 nm	<i>L</i> *	<i>a</i> *	<i>b</i> *	<i>K/S</i> at 400 nm
0	92.84	-0.04	4.54	0	69.85	3.35	15.54	1.50
0.25	92.62	-0.18	4.95	0.01	58.65	6.62	19.32	4.97
0.50	92.75	-0.15	5.45	0.02	56.32	7.23	18.24	5.28
0.75	92.28	-0.12	5.78	0.03	55.48	7.36	18.75	5.63
1.0	91.89	-0.16	5.83	0.04	55.58	6.14	18.12	5.72

untreated fabrics. It was observed that the *K/S* values increased gradually with an increase in the concentration of chitosan. The results indicated that chitosan treatment on fabric provided more active sites for dyeing than untreated fabrics. These can be explained that natural dyes contain unsaturated moiety bearing ionisable groups such as hydroxyl and carboxylic groups. In water with right pH value, they become water soluble due to their presence in anionic forms. Cotton by its nature is negatively charged in water, thus exhibiting poor absorption for natural dyes due to repulsion effect. The application of chitosan could help to improve the absorption of natural dyes by the cationic characteristic property. As a result, chitosan treated cotton is anticipated to favorably absorb natural dyes through the ionic interaction mechanism between dye-anions and fiber-cations. However, treatment of chitosan affected to colour of fabrics. Chitosan made

Fig. 5. Surface colour strength (*K/S* values) of dyed cotton fabrics after pre, post and simultaneous mordanting methods.

chitosan and untreated as shown in Table 2. Comparison of the results in Table 2 showed that the chitosan treated cotton fabrics had a higher depth of shade (*K/S* value) than those of the untreated fabrics for all mordants as shown in Fig. 6. This result indicated that chitosan provided more active dyeing sites on fabric surface.

Table 2. Effect of mordants on dyeing properties of dyed fabrics with and without chitosan treatment

Mordant	Without chitosan treatment					With chitosan treatment				
	CIE L^* a^* b^*			K/S value	Colour obtained	CIE L^* a^* b^*			K/S value	Colour obtained
	L^*	a^*	b^*			L^*	a^*	b^*		
Without mordant	47.73	4.81	18.21	3.45						
Potassium dichromate	71.34	3.45	28.64	5.32						
Ferrous sulphate	53.45	5.66	12.34	11.35						
Cooper sulphate	65.56	4.15	29.64	9.01						
Nickel sulphate	58.37	3.74	21.53	5.23						
Alum	67.25	-2.45	24.57	6.12						
Stannous chloride	47.29	11.45	16.62	7.68						

Fig. 6. Effect of chitosan on dyed cotton fabrics.

Fastness properties for the dyed cotton fabrics : Washing fastness (WF) and Light fastness (LF) results of the dyed fabrics with and without chitosan treatment are indicated in Table 3. Dyed cotton fabric treated with chitosan improved both washing and light fastness. In addition, the results indicate that the use of mordants also improved

Table 3. Fastness values of both chitosan treated and untreated dyed cotton

Mordant	Fastness			
	Untreated dyed cotton fabric		Chitosan treated dyed cotton fabric	
	WF	LF	WF	LF
Without mordant	3	II	4	III
K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	3	II	4	III
FeSO ₄	4	III/IV	4/5	IV
CuSO ₄	4	III	4/5	IV-V
NiSO ₄	3	II	4	IV
Alum	3/4	III	4	IV-V
SnCl ₂	3	II/III	3-4	IV

the fastness property of the dyed fabric. This may be due to greater complex-forming ability of the metal ions with dye molecules.

Conclusions

The purpose of this work was to study the effect of chitosan on the dyeing properties of barks of *Odina woderia* on cotton fabric. From this study it is concluded that, chitosan can improve the colour intensity on the cotton fabric. This may be due to the creation of more active dyeing sites by chitosan on the fabric surface. It was observed that chitosan treated fabrics not only provide better depth of shade, also provided better fastness properties. Use of different mordants and the mordanting methods affected the depth of the shade on the dyed fabrics differently.

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